

International Rice Genetic Survey. Copies of the lists were sent to the senior rice breeder of each research center, with the request that he provide each variety's cross, and add new varieties not recorded and the year of release.

We then plotted the percentages of new varieties that were progeny of major gene sources released from 1965 to 1970, from 1971 to 1975, and from 1976 to 1980.

The most heavily used semidwarf parents in crosses were Taichung Native 1 (TN1) and IR8. The other semidwarf parents were categorized as *locally developed* (bred by the national

programs); *other IRRI* (any IRRI cultivar other than IR 8); and *introduced from another country* (for example if Sona, an Indian semidwarf, were used in Indonesian crosses).

TN1 was used in 22% of all the crosses analyzed for 1965-67, and appeared as a parent of 40% of the new varieties released in the same nations by 1970 (see figure). The steady decline in its use as a parent in the subsequent decade was matched by a corresponding decline in its appearance as a direct parent of new varieties released.

IR8 was involved in about 20% of the crosses made in the mid-1960s and was

a parent of about 25% of the varieties released 5 or 6 years later. Its use in crosses increased and then declined; so did its subsequent appearance as a parent of varieties. Breeders had almost stopped using IR8 as a parent by 1975, but it was a parent of 24% of the varieties released from that time until 1980.

The strongest trend found in the 1975 survey was the increasing use of locally developed semidwarfs as parents—from 0 to about 50% from 1965 to 1975. But of the subsequent varieties, only about 20% are progeny of those crosses. Most of the local semidwarf parents were progeny of IR8 or TN1. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Sheath rot incidence and chaffy grain percentage on some popular rices

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The incidence of sheath rot of rice and percentage of resulting chaffiness on some popular varieties grown in the Chhattisgarh region of MP in 1979

kharif were recorded. Nine varieties were grown in a replicated trial with fertilizer applied at 60-40-20 kg NPK/ha with 3 replications/variety.

The disease incidence was assessed by observing for sheath rot symptoms 10 plants from 3 patches selected for each replication. The percentage of infection was calculated by counting the infected and healthy panicles for each plant (see table).

The infected panicles that showed sheath rot symptoms were randomly collected from the plots and pooled. Because neck rot infection also increases chaffy grain production, care was taken to select neck rot-free panicles. The chaffy and filled grains of 10 panicles were counted. The healthy panicles with no sheath rot or neck rot served as control. The percentage of chaffy grains was higher in the diseased panicles than in the healthy ones.

Percentage of sheath rot incidence and chaffy grains developed. Madhya Pradesh, India.

Variety	Panicle infection (%)	Chaffy grains (%) on	
		Diseased panicles	Healthy panicles
Phakuna	28.8	31.0	8.2
Madhuri	31.2	49.5	9.4
Anupama	32.0	45.8	8.9
Jaya	37.2	32.6	7.5
Kranti	38.0	37.5	11.5
Patel 85	49.5	38.0	12.0
Pragati	53.2	42.0	10.5
Bangoli 5	62.7	30.1	11.0
Patel 17	72.5	48.0	15.0

Patel 17 had maximum incidence and Phalguna minimum. Bangoli 5 had more infection than Phalguna, but the latter had a higher percentage of chaffiness.

Similar observations were made on Patel 17 and Anupama. This indicates that the time of panicle infection may play an important role in chaffy grain production. ■

Outbreak of sheath rot on rice

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During late kharif 1978-79, an outbreak of sheath rot (caused by *Acrocyndrium oryzae*) occurred at Nellore. In October, entries in the national screening nursery were planted singly in 2 rows, each 3 m long. A spacing of 20 x 15 cm was adopted. Urea at 150 kg N/ha was applied in 3 equal splits. Sheath rot was observed at the panicle initiation stage. Unusual rains in December (153 mm), in addition to cool moist weather with

relative humidity of 95% and above on many days, helped spread the disease.

The rot appeared on the uppermost leaf sheaths enclosing the young panicles. Oblong lesions on the leaf sheath coalesced quickly and covered most of the sheath. Among 673 entries tested, 124 recorded clear susceptible reactions (score 5-9). In these susceptible entries almost every panicle was damaged by the fungus. Panicles either remained within the leaf sheath or emerged only partially. Young panicles rotted completely. Profuse powdery growth of the fungus was found inside affected leaf sheaths.

Sheath rot-resistant cultures (score 0–3) from India. Nellore. India.

IET no.	Designation	Cross	Disease score ^a		
			Nellore	Rajendra-nagar	Patna
5938	CN44-33-3	NC1626/T(N)1	0	0	3
6470	TNAU18620	IR20/8CII-6-3	3	0	0
6487	MR343-434-1	SR26 B/Waner 1	3	0	1
6754	OR129-1	OR10-26/RPW6-13	0	0	3
6775	OR149-7148-268	(MNP36/CR12)/Pankaj	0	3	0
6780	CR208-6467	Jagannath/Jayanthi	0	0	0
6781	CR208-7446	” ”	0	0	0
6782	CR208-6462	” ”	0	0	1
6830	IGP-1-2	Pankaj/Kamod 253	0	3	3
6927	RP992-30-10-6-1	Palman 579/IET2508	3	3	–

^aStandard Evaluation System for Rice scale of 1–9: 1 = less than 1% (of tillers affected), 3 = 1–5%.

Sheath rot has been known to cause up to 85% loss in yield. At Nellore no seed could be collected from some entries because all panicles were completely damaged. Similar incidence

of sheath rot during the same season was reported at Rajendranagar and Patna. Ten entries were found resistant in all the three locations where disease pressure was high (see table). ■

CAS 209—a new variety for differentiating virulence of *X. oryzae*

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The work to identify rice varieties suitable for differentiating the virulence of *Xanthomonas oryzae* has been done at IRRI since 1976. CAS 209 from Senegal (IRRI Acc. no. 15793) showed susceptibility to strains of virulence groups I and III but varied reactions to group II strains. When evaluated against PXO 79, a strain of group II, CAS 209 was found susceptible, but was resistant to PXO 86 of the same virulence group. On the basis of this reaction, strains of virulence group II are suspected to be heterogeneous because of a lack of matching resistance or susceptibility in the set of differentials identified earlier.

Subsequently, a test designed to confirm the resistance or susceptibility of a cultivar to group II strains demonstrated that the strains could be further classified into two groups based on their virulence to CAS 209 and to their reaction to other differential varieties. Among 16 of group II strains evaluated, 5 were virulent to CAS 209 and 11 were avirulent. CAS 209, therefore, serves as a distinct variety for differentiation. While it is susceptible to

groups I and III strains, it is completely resistant to some group II strains and susceptible to others. It is susceptible to the five pathotypes in Japan. ■

Amendments to *Acrocyndrium oryzae* spore suspension to induce sheath rot infection of rice

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The spraying of spore suspensions is usually an efficient inoculation technique for most foliar fungus diseases. But the method gave negative results for rice sheath rot in previous greenhouse studies. Because spraying a spore

suspension is a rapid, practical, and convenient inoculation technique, more experiments with various amendments were conducted to improve the technique.

Seedlings of IR1487-372-1-1 (susceptible breeding line) were planted in 6.2-inch (15.75-cm) diameter Wagner pots (3 seedlings/pot) and grown in the phytotron. After 10 weeks they were transferred to the glasshouse. The potted plants were divided into two lots (whole plots). One lot was treated with silicon carbide powder (600 grit carborundum) before inoculation, and the other lot was left untreated. Carborundum was mixed with water (1 g/100 ml) and then sprayed on the plants at 19 lb (1.34 kg/cm²) of pressure, starting from the boot and proceeding to the flag leaf. Each lot was further subdivided into 10 groups of 4 pots each to accommodate these subplot treatments: 25, 50, and 75% nutrient solution; 25 and 50% beef extract-peptone solution; 0.125% agar, 0.5% gelatin; 0.1% Tween 20; distilled water, and noninoculated.

Spores of *Acrocyndrium oryzae* from 1-week-old cultures were dislodged and suspended in the various solutions. They were used to inoculate both the carborundum-sprayed and nonsprayed plants. Inoculated plants were kept inside the glasshouse until sheath rot symptoms developed.

A spore suspension in 25% beef extract-peptone solution was the most effective subplot treatment: 88.3% of the carborundum-treated plants and 28.8% of the tillers/plant exhibited sheath rot symptoms (see table). Sheath rot

Percent sheath rot infection as influenced by various spore suspension amendments on carborundum-treated and nontreated plants. IRRI, 1980.

Treatment	Carborundum-treated		Nontreated	
	Infected plants (%)	Infected tillers (%)	Infected plants (%)	Infected tillers (%)
25% nutrient solution	0	0	0	0
50% nutrient solution	0	0	0	0
75% nutrient solution	0	0	0	0
25% beef extract-peptone solution	83.3	28.8	0	0
50% beef extract-peptone solution	33.3	10.3	16.6	2.2
0.125% agar	16.6	1.4	0	0
0.5% gelatin	0	0	0	0
0.1% Tween 20	8.3	0.8	0	0
Distilled water	8.3	1.0	0	0
Noninoculated	0	0	0	0